

Advanced Manufacturing of Biobased products for urban outdoor applications through iNnovative CharactErisation, digital technologies, and circular approach.

Deliverable

D5.2 Data Management Plan – Update I

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Disclaimer

The sole responsibility for the content of this publication lies with the AMBIANCE project and in no way reflects the views of the European Union.

Abstract

The AMBIANCE Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the observed data that are collected and processed during the lifespan of the project, while providing the overview of available research data, access, data management and terms of use. The DMP reflects the current state of the discussions, plans and ambitions of the partners. It includes the preliminary scenario of data set definitions and expected results (from M1 to M18) and will be updated and implemented with new datasets and results during the lifespan of AMBIANCE (at M36 and at M48)

Moreover, AMBIANCE project supports Open Science paradigm in Horizon EUROPE, that aims to promote cooperative work and systematic sharing of knowledge and tools as early and widely as possible in the process. To ensure the correctness and fully description and management the data management life cycle, the Horizon Europe DMP template has been take as guideline for the writing of AMBIANCE DMP. The current version of the DMP is a first update of the preliminary version of the document, published at M6 that will be updated and augmented with new datasets and results during the lifespan of AMBIANCE.

For completing the DMP deliverable, partners must provide inputs following the HEU template as well as the Data Set Template, which will be the basis to fill in and expand in the following months. In fact, the consortium partners will be requested to investigate and provide more detailed information on their produced data and whether these are discoverable, accessible, assessable, and intelligible, useable (beyond the original purpose) and interoperable.

List of Acronyms

Additive Manufacturing	AM
Comma Separated Values	CSV
Computer-Aided Design	CAD
Computer Numerical Control	CNC
Consortium Agreement	CA
Database	DB
Data Management Plan	DMP
Decision Support System	DSS
Description Of Actions	DoA
Differential Scanning Calorimetry	DSC
Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication	DEC
European Commission	EC
Fibre Bragg Grating	FBG
Fiber Optic Sensor	FOS
Findable, Accessible, Identifiable, Reusable	FAIR
Fused Particle Fabrication	FPF
General Data Protection Regulation	GDPR
Geographic Information System	GIS
Grant Agreement	GA
Horizon Europe	HEU
Intellectual Property Rights	IPR
Life Cycle Assessment	LCA
Machine Learning	ML
Microsoft	MS
Persistent Identifier	PID
Personal Computer	PC
Relational Database Management Systems	RDBMS
Research Data Management	RDM
Terahertz	THz
Thermal Gravimetric Analysis	TGA
To Be Defined	TBD
Work Package	WP

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I Introduction

Good data management is not a goal in itself, but rather is the key conduit leading to knowledge discovery and innovation, and to subsequent data and knowledge integration and reuse by the community after the data publication process. The amount of data generated by research projects continuously increases, however re-using the data for further research purposes and thus maximising the benefit deriving from the research investments still represents a hard challenge. Data needs to be properly collected, annotated, and filed in such a way they will be available in a long-term period and will be re-used for downstream investigations, either alone or in combination with newly generated data (in line with the European Commission, H2020 and HEU guidelines).

The Data Management Plan (DMP) fills this purpose as it describes and characterises the observed data that are collected and processed during the lifetime of a project. This document is the status quo plan and determination of the partners with assumptions of data set definitions and draft results (up to M18 of the project) that will be updated and improved continuously during AMBIANCE lifespan.

I.1 The Data Management Plan (DMP) in Horizon Europe

According to the guidelines of the EC, the DMP is “the key element of good data management. A DMP describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by a Horizon Europe project”¹.

The DMP is a document that outlines the **procedures and methodologies of data treatment during the project and how data will be used and shared after the project ends**. It deals with the generation and discovery of data, their collection, evaluation by quality assurance, classification, organization, and documentation. Dissemination and sharing policies are also addressed within the DMP.

The process of creation of the DMP respects some **golden rules** that ensure the successful management of research data arising from the project. W. K. Michener in his article “Ten Simple Rules for Creating a Good Data Management Plan”² well outlines the building process of the DMP, which starts with the identification of the data to be collected (1), followed by the definition on how the data will be organized (2), documented (3), how data quality will be assured (4), the strategy adopted to preserve and store the data collected (5), the data policies adopted (6), ending with the rules for the dissemination of the data and the appointment of the roles and responsibilities of data management (7).

The AMBIANCE DMP is at its first update and much information are still not available. However, since the first version of the DMP at M6 we have a first characterization of the data partners expect to collect. Namely:

- *the types of data*: text, spreadsheets, software, algorithms, pictures, videos, audio files;
- *the volume of data*: data management activities might be influenced by the number of the data to be handled;
- *the sources*: stakeholders or research centers that wish to re-use the data generated by the project are interested in the source of the data, if they are proprietary, derive from other research studies, are subject to restrictions or can be freely used;
- *the data and file formats*: non-proprietary formats are preferred as they ensure the accessibility to the data for the long term (examples could be Comma Separated Values - CSV).

As already anticipated, the DMP is a living document that must be revised during the project lifecycle. Therefore, contents and information on data will be periodically updated with the missing data to achieve a comprehensive roadmap on the use of data generated and used within the project. The AMBIANCE Grant Agreement establishes updates at M6, M18, M36 and M48. This version represents the first update at M18 with respect to the initial version published at M6.

The definition of the way the data will be organized should be addressed as well and it is strongly influenced by the volume of the data generated and used within the project. Larger data volumes and usage constraints

¹ European Commission, Guidelines to the rules on open access to scientific publications and open access to research data in H2020, March 2017

² Michener, William K. "Ten simple rules for creating a good data management plan." *PLoS computational biology* 11.10 (2015): e1004525.

may require the use of Relational DataBase Management Systems (RDBMS) for linked data tables like ORACLE or mySQL, or a Geographic Information System (GIS) for geospatial data layers like ArcGIS, GRASS, or QGIS, while a small number of data could be effectively managed with commercial or open source spreadsheet programs like Excel and OpenOffice Calc. The data organization will be defined once we will have a clearer scenario of the types of data and the volume of data collected within the project. To do so, a Workshop will be organized with partners.

The documentation of the data by means of proper metadata is fundamental to ensure that data will be discoverable, usable and properly cited by those who will look for them and use them for further research purposes. Indeed, metadata means "data about data". **Metadata is defined as the data providing information about one or more aspects of the data**; it is used to summarize basic information about data which can make tracking and working with specific data easier. In this project, structural and descriptive metadata will be deployed to define formats, types, versions and relationships between digital data and to identify the data through some of their characteristics, like data of collection, volume, name, authors/owners and keywords.

Quality control and quality assurance of research data will be defined at a later stage, when the characterisation of research data will be more complete, and it will be in line with the quality assurance procedures defined in "D6.3 - Quality assurance and risk management plan".

Data storage and preservation strategy will be an important topic that the DMP will address, by answering to the following questions:

- How long will the data be accessible?
- How will data be stored and protected over the duration of the project?
- How will data be preserved and made available for future use?

The answers to these questions are expected to vary from one partner to another due to several factors. The internal data policy of each partner will influence the possibility to make some of the research data collected public or not. Moreover, if the partners will make the data available to be consulted by other researchers after the end of the project, the storage may depend on the type of data generated, indeed some of them may need to be kept for a short time as they are extremely repeatable, while if they are strongly variable from one experiment to another might need to be stored for a very long time. The data that will receive the authorization by the owners to be published and available for others to use will be stored within online collaborative platforms accessible by the project consortium and will also be uploaded on online repositories like Zenodo (<http://www.zenodo.org/>).

The DMP will also include explicit policy statements about how data will be managed and shared. Such policies include the licensing or sharing arrangements that pertain to the use of pre-existing materials; the plans for licensing, sharing, and embargoing (i.e., limiting use by others for a period) data, code, and other materials; the legal and ethical restrictions on access and use of human subject and other sensitive data. The policies will be in line with what has been stated in the Consortium Agreement with respect to the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and the joint ownership of the results and the data beyond them, and to what the GDPR and the Ethics Requirements deliverables report with regards to the Personal Data treatment and the treatment of data deriving from the involvement of human beings in the project experiments.

The IPR and non-disclosure statements will be very important for the dissemination actions taken by the project partners. The DMP will be compliant with the statements of the Consortium Agreement (CA) and the Ethics Deliverables in defining when, how and which data will be made available. Dissemination actions will range from posting the data on social media and the project website, to publishing the data in online repositories and in scientific journals.

1.2 Connection to Open Science

Horizon Europe moves beyond open access to open science for which it features a comprehensive policy implemented from the proposal stage to project reporting. Open science is an approach based on open cooperative work and systematic sharing of knowledge and tools as early and widely as possible in the process. It has the potential to increase the quality and efficiency of research and accelerate the advancement of knowledge and innovation by sharing results, making them more reusable and improving their reproducibility. It entails the involvement of all relevant knowledge actors.

The DMP is strongly connected to open science practices in HEU because it is a cornerstone for responsible management of research outputs, notably data. Indeed, the DMP is the most important tool for Research data management (RDM). The RDM is mandatory in Horizon Europe for projects generating or reusing data and it is the process within the research lifecycle that includes the data collection or acquisition, organisation, curation, storage, (long-term) preservation, security, quality assurance, allocation of persistent identifiers (PIDs), provision of metadata in line with disciplinary requirements, licencing, and rules and procedures for sharing of data. The RDM is an essential element in any project that generates, collects or re-uses data. Carefully planning for the needs of the data that proponents are likely to encounter during the project is a best practice.

Furthermore, **data management should be in line with the FAIR principles³**, to ensure that researchers can find, access and re-use each other's data, maximising the effectiveness and reproducibility of the research undertaken. The RDM, in line with the FAIR principles, is a requirement that should be carried out regardless of whether the data generated and re-used in the project is intended to be openly accessible, or if access restrictions are foreseen. FAIR data is not equivalent to open data (publicly available to everyone to access and reuse). Data can (and should) be FAIR even when access is restricted. The RDM and the FAIR principles can be applied to research outputs other than data (i.e., workflows, protocols, software, samples, etc).

1.3 Objectives of the Data Management Plan

AMBIANCE project aims to develop new and advanced bio-based products, characterized by a high or total bio-based material contents and considering the different alternatives for recirculation. Special attention will be paid to the optimization of product manufacturing of bio-based materials. Besides, the use of Digital Twin technologies will enhance the development of materials and products and the remanufacturing of such bio-based goods, and it will optimize manufacturing processes and enhance production quality of such novel applications by leveraging Internet of Things and Artificial Intelligence technologies.

Considering the whole amount of data that AMBIANCE is expected to generate, the purpose of the DMP is to define the proper management of project research data and of data subjects in compliance with the EC recommendations and national and international regulations and guidelines on the use of data.

The Plan is intended as a roadmap illustrating how data arisen from project research lines will be treated throughout the project lifetime and beyond once it will be finished. The AMBIANCE DMP will provide a vehicle for conveying information to and setting expectations for the project team during the different stages of the project. The plan will be a living document that is periodically reviewed according to the new data gathered, the needs and any changes in protocols (e.g., metadata, storage) and policies.

1.4 AMBIANCE Data Management Plan

AMBIANCE project is the result of a successful proposal (number 101058406) submitted on 23/09/2021 to the European Commission. The consortium signed the Grant Agreement and thus jointly undertook to execute the project. The mandate of the project is to execute the work described in accordance with the signed contract (Grant Agreement) and its annexes, within budgetary and schedule constraints. This document is related to what is described in the Description of Actions (DoA) (AMBIANCE GA) as deliverable D5.2 Data Management Plan_Update I and is related to WP5 Impact Enhancement.

The AMBIANCE project is focused on the development of sustainable bio-based materials for outdoor applications. The results obtained during the project might represent a strong improvement towards EU sustainable goals. From this point of view, AMBIANCE consortium is aware of the importance to share FAIR and reliable data among academy community with the aim to push the research on novel sustainable products and manufacturing processes. Stick to the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”, AMBIANCE consortium will implement an open science policy that allow to share with EU research communities the data generated during the project.

Furthermore, attention will be paid to research data management starting from the beginning of the project so to make sure that results can be findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable (FAIR). This includes careful screening of relevant standards (and appropriate selections that ensure widest possible compatibility and

³ FAIR data are data that are curated to satisfy the principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. For further reading: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

outreach), but also developing models for data sharing, while protecting privacy of users and providing security of IP and business of the involved companies. The DPM of the AMBIANCE project has been prepared following the template provided by the European Commission of the “Data Management Plan”⁴.

The following chapters contain a second updated version of the data sets that will be generated within the project lifespan provided by parents (updated up until M18). Partners were, in fact, asked to update the original data sets presented in D5.1 “*Data Management Plan_Initial version*” at M6 with new data information.

All partners were able to provide updated information. General information about data (types, format, re-use, origins, size, etc); data strategies (FAIR data); allocation of resources and data security are provided.

2 Data Set Template

The AMBIANCE DMP describes the observed data that are collected and processed during the lifetime of the project while providing the overview of available research data, access, data management and terms of use. The DMP reflects the current state of the discussions, plans and ambitions of the partners. It includes the M18 scenario of data set definitions and expected results and will be updated and implemented with new datasets and results during the lifespan of AMBIANCE.

Moreover, the AMBIANCE project, when possible, will use the Open Research Europe in Horizon Europe that aims to improve access to and re-use of research data with a special focus on the need to balance openness and protection of scientific information.

The intention of the DMP is to describe numerical model or observation datasets collected or created by AMBIANCE project. The information listed below reflects **the conception and design of the individual partners in the different work packages at M18 of the project**. The data register will deliver information according to information detailed in Annex 1 (Part A) of the Grant Agreement Document (GA):

- **Data set reference and name:** identifier for the data set to be produced.
- **Data set description:** descriptions of the data that will be generated or collected, its origin or source (in case it is collected), nature, scale, to whom it could be useful and whether it underpins a scientific publication. Information on the existence (or not) of similar data and the possibilities for integration and reuse.
- **Partners’ activities and responsibilities:** partner owner of the device, in charge of the data collection, data analysis and/or data storage, and WPs and tasks it is involved.
- **Standards and metadata:** reference to existing suitable standards of the discipline. If these do not exist, an outline on how and what metadata will be created. Format and estimated volume of data.
- **Data exploitation and share:** description of how data will be shared, including access procedures and policy, embargo periods (if any), outlines of technical mechanisms for dissemination and necessary software and other tools for enabling re-use, and definition of whether access will be widely open or restricted to specific groups. Identification of the repository where data will be stored, if already existing and identified, indicating the type of repository (institutional, standard repository for the discipline, etc.) and if this information will be confidential (only for members of the Consortium and the Commission Services) or public. In case of dataset cannot be shared, the reasons for this should be mentioned (e.g., ethical reasons, rules of personal data, intellectual property, commercial reasons, privacy-related, security-related).
- **Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup):** description of the procedures that will be put in place for long-term preservation of the data. Indication of how long the data should be preserved, what is its approximated end volume, what the associated costs are and how these are planned to be covered.

Such data can be anonymised for statistical or other purposes and shared with open access, which could be further analysed and provide the possibility to extract information and knowledge from them. Each dataset can

⁴ <https://enspire.science/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Horizon-Europe-Data-Management-Plan-Template.pdf>

be accompanied by several metadata (e.g., type, gender, age, etc...) which can support various kinds of historical data analysis.

2.1 Data set identification by partner organisations

All partners need to identify the data that will be produced in the different project activities they are involved in and must provide an overview on the nature and details for each dataset.

To do so, partners have been asked to update the table filled in at the M6 version of the DMP with new or updated data they expect to treat in their activities according to the WPs and tasks they are involved in. The table template to be used is shown in **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**

Table 1- Partner XX data identification

Data Identification	
Data set description	<i>Describe the existing or intended data, indicating their origin, nature and order of magnitude.</i>
Type of data: qualitative or quantitative?	<i>Motivate the creation of new data sets and their added value.</i>
Order of magnitude	
Provenance of data: sources	<i>Describe whether the data come from interviews, surveys or are extracted from disciplinary archives, databases and / or other projects, devices, machines.</i>
Nature and formats of data	<i>Describe nature and format of data: a) text documents (DOC, ODF, PDF, TXT, etc); b) images (JPG, GIF, SVG, PNG, TIFF); c) video / film (MPEG, AVI, WMV, MP4); d) audio recordings (MP3, WAV, AIFF, OGG, etc); e) structured data (HTML, JSON, TEX, XML, RDF); f) tables (CSV, ODS, TSV, XLS, SAS, Stata, SPSS portable); g) source codes (C, CSS, JavaScript, Java, etc); h) configuration data (INI, CONF, etc); i) database (MS Access, MySql, Oracle, etc);</i>
New data set value	<i>Motivating the creation of the new dataset, defining its added value for the scientific community or other recipients</i>
Audio-visual material	<i>In case of video, indicate the duration (the data is useful for planning the costs design and archiving)</i>
Partners Activities & Responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device producing the data	<i>Partner of the project owner of the device/software producing the data</i>
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	
WPs and tasks	
Standards and Metadata	
Metadata standards and data documentation	<i>Describe the type of metadata with reference to standards and documentation</i>
Methodology for data collection/generation	<i>Describe the methodologies of data collection and production during the research process. 1. Who and how it collects data; 2. Who and how it structures and stores them; 3. Who and how he processes them; 4. Who and how he distributes them. Refer to regulations or practices in force in the scientific community of reference</i>
Data exploitation & sharing	

Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	
Data ownership	<i>Who is the owner of the data? Is another organization contributing to the data development? Are you re-using some pre-existing data?</i>
Suitability for sharing	<i>Public/confidential/limited access</i>
Data utility	<i>How will this data shared/made accessible for verification and re-use</i>
Open research data pilot	<i>Can data be uploaded in an open research data pilot? When?</i>
Embargo periods (if any)	
Archiving & preservation (including storage and backup)	
Managing, storing and curating data	<i>Please describe the modality of: storage; backup; transmission; data processing in the short and medium term, with references to practices, standards and regulations where applicable.</i>
Data Storage	<i>Please indicate: where data will be stored if the conservation concerns the whole collected data or only part of them, for how long data will be stored</i>

2.1.1 Partners’ data identification

The following tables report partners’ update feedback on data at M18 of project activities. The data analysis follows the structure presented in **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**

2.1.1.1 Partner 1: ITAINNOVA

Table 2 - Partner ITAINNOVA data identification

Data Identification	
Data set description Type of data: qualitative or quantitative? Order of magnitude	<p><i>Describe the existing or intended data, indicating their origin, nature and order of magnitude.</i></p> <p>Existing data include materials composition and properties etc., obtained from literatures and from previous tests performed by ITAINNOVA of other materials for comparison with those to be used and/or developed in the Ambiance project; the existing data can have a size between 1 MB to 10 GB.</p> <p>Intended data include material compositions, processing procedures and properties, etc., of the biomaterials & formulations to be used and/or developed in the Ambiance project; the intended data can have a size between 1 MB to 10 GB.</p>
Provenance of data: sources	<p><i>Describe whether the data come from interviews, surveys or are extracted from disciplinary archives, databases and / or other projects, devices, machines.</i></p> <p>The data to be generated in the Ambiance project based on the biomaterials & formulations to be used and/or developed will come from materials processing, materials design, manufacturing, testing, simulation and demonstration. Existing data will mostly come from literature and previous digital twin developments, new tests, and trials from different previous projects where ITAINNOVA has been involved.</p>
Nature and formats of data	<p><i>Describe nature and format of data:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) text documents (DOC, ODF, PDF, TXT, etc); b) images (JPG, GIF, SVG, PNG, TIFF); c) video / film (MPEG, AVI, WMV, MP4); d) audio recordings (MP3, WAV, AIFF, OGG, etc); e) simulation models (cas, rocky, dat, inp, odb, db, rst, py, exe, sh, txt) f) tables (CSV, ODS, TSV, XLS, SAS, Stata, SPSS portable); g) extensions from Fluent, Abaqus, Ansys and ROM (.py, .bat, C, CSS, Javascript, Java, etc)
New data set value	<p><i>Motivate the creation of the new dataset, defining its added value for the scientific community or other recipients.</i></p> <p>The biomaterials to be used and the formulations to be developed in the Ambiance project will further unlock the potential of renewable raw materials in applications and in new products, which will further facilitate the reduction of carbon footprint in the targeted sectors and fields. Moreover, the generated data will not only enrich the scientific and technological content in the Ambiance project itself, but also increase know-how of scientific community and industry about sustainable materials, manufacturing, and production.</p> <p>The computational models developed in the Ambiance project will contribute to the digitalization of the involved companies towards a more sustainable, efficient, and digital industry. Moreover, the development of these models will also help to advance in the scientific area of simulation.</p>
Audio-visual material	<p><i>In case of video, indicate the duration (the data is useful for planning the costs design and archiving.</i></p> <p>Different videos with an approximated maximum duration of 3-5 min (experimental video records, simulation animations...)</p>

Partners Activities & Responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device producing the data	Data property of the consortium companies (MONDO, SETGA, PODCOMP). The data not intended to be commercially exploited and that might be published either in scientific journals, or by other dissemination channels will be always previously approved by the data owner.
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	AIMEN for SETGA data, RISE for PODCOMP data
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	CORE
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	
WPs and tasks	WP1 (Task 1.1/1.2/1.3), WP2 (Task 2.1/2.2/2.3/2.4/2.5), WP3 (Task 3.1/3.2/3.3/3.4/3.5/3.6), WP4 (Task 4.1/4.2/4.3/4.4), WP5 (Task 5.1/5.2/5.3/5.4/5.5), WP6 (Task 6.1/6.2/6.3), WP7
Standards and Metadata	
Metadata standards and data documentation	To be defined
Methodology for data collection/generation	<i>Describe the methodologies of data collection and production during the research process.</i> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Who and how it collects data; ITAINNOVA experimental technical managers will gather the data coming from experimental trials and will store them in an internal server (ITAINNOVA) and in a common cloud server (Teams) with restricted access. Computational technical managers will gather data from simulations, models, algorithms, and will store them in an internal server (ITAINNOVA) and in a common cloud server (Teams) with restricted access. 2. Who and how it structures and stores them; Technical managers from ITAINNOVA will structure and store data in the project folder in ITAINNOVA OneDrive and in the defined place in the project folder shared by the Ambiance consortium 3. Who and how he processes them; appointed responsible from CORE with ITAINNOVA support will allocate work to different researchers and engineers who will specifically obtain and process the data. 4. Who and how he distributes them; Internal distributions: Technical managers from ITAINNOVA via technical presentations, reports, etc. 5. External dissemination: Coordination personnel from ITAINNOVA following the communication & dissemination rules at ITAINNOVA, Ambiance consortium and EC.
Data exploitation & sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	The RSC will use the data to decide whether a defective part/product should return to a previous production stage. ITAINNOVA will use the data for fabrication process optimization, improving product quality, new materials research, and reduce the costs associated to production and material consumption.
Data ownership	<i>Who is the owner of the data?</i> ITAINNOVA <i>Is another organization contributing to the data development?</i>

	<p>Companies members of the Ambiance consortium (MONDO, SETGA and PODCOMP. In the future, AIMEN and CORE).</p> <p><i>Are you re-using some pre-existing data?</i> No</p>
Suitability for sharing	<i>Public/confidential/limited access:</i> confidential for external use but can be shared to some AMBIANCE consortium partners if required.
Data utility	<i>How will this data shared/made accessible for verification and re-use:</i> Mainly through scientific publication on peer reviewed journals, presentations in conferences and demonstrations in workshops, always observing confidentiality agreements and previously consulting involved parties.
Open research data pilot	<i>Can data be uploaded in an open research data pilot? When?</i> The data can be uploaded in an open research data pilot if and when they will be published in e.g., journal papers, conference abstracts/presentations, always observing confidentiality agreements and previously consulting involved parties.
Embargo periods (if any)	No
Archiving & preservation (including storage and backup)	
Managing, storing, and curating data	<p><i>Please describe the modality of: storage, backup, transmission, data processing in the short and medium term, with references to practices, standards and regulations where applicable.</i></p> <p>All data generated by RISE will be collected, stored, and backed up in an internal server of ITAINNOVA, and those who will be shared will be placed in folders in Teams and OneDrive.</p>
Data Storage	<p><i>Please indicate: where data will be stored? the conservation concerns the whole collected data or only part of them? For how long data will be stored?</i></p> <p>At least the time that the EU Commission recommends for each project.</p>

2.1.1.2 Partner 2: AIMEN

Table 3- Partner AIMEN data identification. Use Case 1 – Mondo

Data Identification	
Data set description Type of data: qualitative or quantitative? Order of magnitude	<i>Describe the existing or intended data, indicating their origin, nature, and order of magnitude.</i> Quantitative data of measurements of multiple filament's geometrical features (e.g. cross section, etc.) will be generated over a defined time frame. The order of magnitude will be a mm. <i>Motivate the creation of new data sets and their added value.</i> These data set will be used for monitoring reproducibility of filament cross section over time.
Provenance of data: sources	<i>Describe whether the data come from interviews, surveys or are extracted from disciplinary archives, databases and / or other projects, devices, machines.</i> A table with filament geometrical features will be generated by a device to be developed in the subtask 3.2.1 UC1 in-line filament monitoring system during extrusion process.
Nature and formats of data	<i>Nature and format of data:</i> b) images (JPG, GIF, SVG, PNG, TIFF); c) video / film (MPEG, AVI, WMV, MP4); f) tables (CSV, ODS, TSV, XLS, SAS, Stata, SPSS portable);
New data set value	<i>Motivating the creation of the new dataset, defining its added value for the scientific community or other recipients.</i> These data set will be used for monitoring reproducibility of filament geometrical features over time at MONDO's use case. Currently, no monitorization is carried out.
Audio-visual material	<i>In case of video, indicate the duration (the data is useful for planning the costs design and archiving).</i>
Partners Activities & Responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device producing the data	AIMEN
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	
WPs and tasks	WP3 / Subtask 3.2.1
Standards and Metadata	
Metadata standards and data documentation	<i>Describe the type of metadata with reference to standards and documentation.</i> Metadata may include timestamp and information related to the manufacturing process.
Methodology for data collection/generation	<i>Describe the methodologies of data collection and production during the research process.</i> 1. AIMEN will obtain the information of cross section of the extruded filaments by machine vision-based methods. 2. AIMEN will create a table of the cross sections of several filaments over time and store it on the dedicated PC of the developed device. 3. AIMEN will organize the data for visualization and reporting. 4. The data will be available for AIMEN and MONDO to monitor the latter use case.
Data exploitation & sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	The data will be used to identify possible defective batches of produced filaments.

Data ownership	AIMEN and MONDO own the produced data – TBD during the project
Suitability for sharing	Confidential
Data utility	<i>How will this data shared/made accessible for verification and re-use.</i>
Open research data pilot	<i>Can data be uploaded in an open research data pilot? When?</i> Public data will be disseminated, when relevant, and agreed with partners. Data would be available in open dissemination research data repositories such as Zenodo.
Embargo periods (if any)	
Archiving & preservation (including storage and backup)	
Managing, storing and curating data	<i>Please describe the modality of storage, backup, transmission, data processing in the short and medium term, with references to practices, standards and regulations where applicable.</i> Storage: locally or on open repository. Backup: AMEN server. Transmission: online repository shared between AIMEN and MONDO. Data processing in the short and medium term: data will be processed to monitor possible filament production defects. Standards and regulations where applicable TBD during the project.
Data Storage	<i>Please indicate: where data will be stored? the conservation concerns the whole collected data or only part of them? For how long data will be stored?</i> Data will be stored locally on the devices' PC and on the servers of AIMEN and MONDO for the duration of the project and the justification period. Part of the data set might be stored on an open data repository – TBD during the project

Table 4 - Partner AIMEN data identification Use Case 2- SETGA

Data Identification	
Data set description Type of data: qualitative or quantitative? Order of magnitude	<i>Describe the existing or intended data, indicating their origin, nature, and order of magnitude.</i> Additive Manufacturing (AM): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3D model of product to be manufactured originated from CAD software. Weight of 3D model file usually around 500kb to 10mb. - Program file containing robot instructions for part manufacturing in robot (FANUC) code. Weight of program file usually around 500kb to 10mb. Manufacturing Monitoring (MM): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thermal images obtained from the extrusion process of the FPF deposition for the bio-based outdoor furniture elements. Information such as temperature about the extrusion process can be retrieved. - Parameters such as speed, printing head position, printing head extrusion parameters etc will be retrieved from PLC Material Characterization (MC): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The data will contain material properties from characterization of small batches of biomaterials formulations and 3D printed samples.
Provenance of data: sources	<i>Describe whether the data come from interviews, surveys or are extracted from disciplinary archives, databases and / or other projects, devices, machines.</i> AM: 3D model file and FANUC Robot code. MM: Thermal data from camera FLIR A70, and other parameter (speed, position) from SIEMENS PLC. MC: data produced by characterization equipment (DSC, TGA, mechanical testing machine, ageing chamber...)

Nature and formats of data	<p><i>Describe nature and format of data:</i></p> <p>AM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3D model file (. step, .stl) - b) FANUC Robot code (.ls, .kl, .tp) <p>MM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - images (BMP, TIFF) - Other parameters in HDF5 <p>MC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reports (.docx, .xlsx, ppt, PDF) - Graphs (.jpg)
New data set value	<p><i>Motivating the creation of the new dataset, defining its added value for the scientific community or other recipients.</i></p> <p>AM: creation of processing window for additive manufacturing process, process parameters gathered in excel spreadsheet.</p> <p>MM: The new dataset will enable the monitor and control the FPF deposition process.</p> <p>MC: evaluation of properties and quality of the printed samples.</p>
Audio-visual material	<p><i>In case of video, indicate the duration (the data is useful for planning the costs design and archiving).</i></p> <p>AM: HD Video of manufacturing (500mb-1gb), timelapse of images.</p>
Partners Activities & Responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device producing the data	AIMEN and ITA
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	AIMEN and CORE
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	AIMEN and CORE
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	AIMEN and CORE
WPs and tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WP2 - WP3 - T3.2.3 - WP3 - T3.3 - WP4
Standards and Metadata	
Metadata standards and data documentation	<p><i>Describe the type of metadata with reference to standards and documentation.</i></p> <p>Metadata may include timestamp and information related to the manufacturing process.</p>
Methodology for data collection/generation	<p><i>Describe the methodologies of data collection and production during the research process.</i></p> <p>AM:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. AM Technician, exports from software CAD/CAM 2. AM Technician, stores in AIMEN server 3. CAD model edited in Solidworks, Robot program edited if necessary in VScode editor. 4. AIMEN shares data via sharepoint. <p>MM:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. AIMEN will collect data from the thermal camera and PLC. 2. AIMEN will structure the data by named it according to the metadata and store it in their server. 3. AIMEN processes and stores it to derive data-based correlations and models. 4. CORE accesses the data saved at AIMEN servers. <p>MC:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Technician, export from characterization equipment. 2. Technician, stores in AIMEN server

	<p>3. Data representation and analysis may be performed by EXCEL or ORIGIN if necessary.</p> <p>4. Data shared through the project's SharePoint</p>
Data exploitation & sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	<p>AM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The RSC will use the data to decide whether a defective part/product should return to a previous production stage. <p>MM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The available data coming from the thermal camera will allow to verify how layer temperature is evolving while printing bio-based outdoor furniture. - <u>Data coming from PLC will help digital twin development (ITA) and data analysis (CORE).</u> <p>MC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The data will provide information for the developing of the AM processing window.
Data ownership	<p><i>Who is the owner of the data?</i> AIMEN/CORE/SETGA/ITA <i>Is another organization contributing to the data development?</i> No <i>Are you re-using some pre-existing data?</i> No</p>
Suitability for sharing	All obtained data can be shared with the rest of the partners interested in it.
Data utility	<i>How will this data shared/made accessible for verification and re-use.</i>
Open research data pilot	<i>Can data be uploaded in an open research data pilot? When?</i> Public data will be disseminated, when relevant, and agreed with partners. Data would be available in open dissemination research data repositories such as Zenodo.
Embargo periods (if any)	
Archiving & preservation (including storage and backup)	
Managing, storing and curating data	<p><i>Please describe the modality of: storage, backup, transmission, data processing in the short and medium term, with references to practices, standards and regulations where applicable.</i></p> <p>Data will be stored and backed up in AIMEN servers following the internal rules that the company has regarding all the projects. Data will be archived in AIMEN servers. MS Teams can be employed to share data.</p>
Data Storage	<p><i>Please indicate: where data will be stored? the conservation concerns the whole collected data or only part of them? For how long data will be stored?</i></p> <p>The data produced during the project is stored, at least, on AIMEN internal servers. In addition, backups will be made to ensure the preservation of the data. Data will be available as it is generated during manufacturing, monitoring, and characterization activities, and until the end of the project. Also, data will be available for a period afterward to be defined.</p>

Table 5 - Partner AIMEN data identification Use Case 3 - PODCOMP

Data Identification	
Data set description Type of data: qualitative or quantitative? Order of magnitude	<p><i>Describe the existing or intended data, indicating their origin, nature and order of magnitude. Motivate the creation of new data sets and their added value.</i></p> <p>Fiber Optic Sensor (FOS) measurements, Fiber Optic Sensor (FOS) data set. Experimental data obtained during the monitoring campaign of the thermoforming manufacturing process. FOS data set will have strain, load, press, or temperature measurements related to the thermoforming process.</p> <p>The creation of new data sets is required to have a process quality controlled by the employment of embedded FOS for temperature and strain, in addition to data analytics solutions.</p>
Provenance of data: sources	<p><i>Describe whether the data come from interviews, surveys or are extracted from disciplinary archives, databases and / or other projects, devices, machines.</i></p> <p>FOS data is obtained during the monitoring activities of the thermoforming manufacturing process. Fiber optic interrogators are the devices employed to generate the FOS data.</p>
Nature and formats of data	<p><i>Describe nature and format of data.</i></p> <p>The nature of the data is raw data obtained during the monitoring, and pre-processed data. Depending on the model of FOS interrogator employed, different files are generated.</p> <p>a) text documents (TXT, JSON, CSV, LOG or HDF5) b) images (JPG, PNG or GIF) Python files (.py) will be employed for data analysis.</p>
New data set value	<p><i>Motivating the creation of the new dataset, defining its added value for the scientific community or other recipients.</i></p> <p>New data set will enable a monitored and controlled manufacturing process.</p>
Audio-visual material	<p><i>In case of video, indicate the duration (the data is useful for planning the costs design and archiving).</i></p>
Partners Activities & Responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device producing the data	AIMEN
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	AIMEN and CORE
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	AIMEN and CORE
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	AIMEN and CORE
WPs and tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - WP3 – T3.2.4 - WP3 – T3.3 - WP4
Standards and Metadata	
Metadata standards and data documentation	<p><i>Describe the type of metadata with reference to standards and documentation.</i></p> <p>Metadata may include the date, timestamp, and information related to the manufacturing process. The internal structure of the files follows a similar pattern, regardless of the file format. There are two main data files, depending on the selected FOS technology.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In the case of distributed sensors, the file contains the time, some measurement parameters, and the measurement data in frequency (transformable to temperature, strain, ...) for each measurement point. - In the case of FBG sensors, each file has a header with measurement parameters, one column with the timestamps of the measurement, and other columns with the wavelength of each sensor.

Methodology for data collection/generation	<p><i>Describe the methodologies of data collection and production during the research process.</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Refer to regulations or practices in force in the scientific community of reference AIMEN collects data using fiber optic interrogators. 2. AIMEN saves data on text or structured files in their servers. 3. CORE accesses to the data saved in AIMEN servers. Also, it processes and stores it to derive data-based correlations and models.
Data exploitation & sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	The available data coming from FOS will be gathered, correlated, processed, and stored in order to derive data-based correlations and models. The accumulated data will be used by both data-driven models (using ML techniques) and physics-based models (ROMs).
Data ownership	<p><i>Who is the owner of the data?</i> AIMEN/CORE/PODCOMP/RISE <i>Is another organization contributing to the data development?</i> No <i>Are you re-using some pre-existing data?</i> No</p>
Suitability for sharing	<p><i>Public/confidential/limited access</i></p> <p>All obtained data can be shared with the rest of the partners interested in it.</p>
Data utility	<i>How will this data shared/made accessible for verification and re-use?</i>
Open research data pilot	<p><i>Can data be uploaded in an open research data pilot? When?</i></p> <p>Public data will be disseminated, when relevant, and agreed with partners. Data would be available in open dissemination research data repositories such as Zenodo.</p>
Embargo periods (if any)	
Archiving & preservation (including storage and backup)	
Managing, storing and curating data	<p><i>Please describe the modality of: storage, backup, transmission, data processing in the short and medium term, with references to practices, standards and regulations where applicable.</i></p> <p>Data will be stored and backed up in AIMEN servers following the internal rules that the company has regarding all the projects. Data will be archived in AIMEN servers. MS Teams can be employed to share data.</p>
Data Storage	<p><i>Please indicate: where data will be stored? the conservation concerns the whole collected data or only part of them? For how long data will be stored?</i></p> <p>The data produced during the project is stored, at least, on AIMEN internal servers. In addition, backups will be made to ensure the preservation of the data. Data will be available as it is generated during monitoring activities, and until the end of the project. Also, data will be available for a period afterward to be defined.</p>

2.1.1.3 Partner 3: CORE

Table 6 - Partner CORE data identification. Use Case 1 – MONDO

Data Identification	
Data set description Type of data: qualitative or quantitative? Order of magnitude	<i>Describe the existing or intended data, indicating their origin, nature, and order of magnitude.</i> Data set description: Machines' best suitable set of parameters and settings provided by DSS. Type of data: Qualitative Order of magnitude: Unknown. More information will be provided in the following versions of the DMP.
Provenance of data: sources	<i>Describe whether the data come from interviews, surveys or are extracted from disciplinary archives, databases and / or other projects, devices, machines.</i> Devices, machines, sensors, cameras.
Nature and formats of data	<i>Describe nature and format of data:</i> Tables (CSV, ODS, TSV, XLS, SAS, Stata, SPSS portable, hdf5) and/or structured data (JSON).
New data set value	<i>Motivating the creation of the new dataset, defining its added value for the scientific community or other recipients.</i> The developed data will consist of the output of Machine Learning (ML) models and will concern the machines' best suitable set of parameters and settings.
Audio-visual material	<i>In case of video, indicate the duration (the data is useful for planning the costs design and archiving).</i> No audio-visual material will be created.
Partners Activities & Responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device producing the data	CORE
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	CORE
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	MONDO
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	CORE
WPs and tasks	WP3 – T3.3, T3.4
Standards and Metadata	
Metadata standards and data documentation	<i>Describe the type of metadata with reference to standards and documentation.</i> No metadata and data documentation will be created
Methodology for data collection/generation	<i>Describe the methodologies of data collection and production during the research process.</i> 1. Who and how it collects data; CORE will collect the data, produced by the ML models. 2. Who and how it structures and stores them; CORE will store the data in distributed DBs (MongoDB, Apache Druid) in JSON format. 3. Who and how he processes them; The data will be processed by MONDO. 4. Who and how he distributes them. The data distribution will be performed by CORE either through streaming protocols (Kafka, MQTT) or RESTful APIs depending on the use case. More information will be provided in the next version of the DMP.
Data exploitation & sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	Optimization of product quality.
Data ownership	<i>Who is the owner of the data?</i> CORE

	<i>Is another organization contributing to the data development? No Are you re-using some pre-existing data? No</i>
Suitability for sharing	Confidential
Data utility	<i>How will this data shared/made accessible for verification and re-use?</i> The data will be available either through streaming protocols (MQTT/Kafka) or RESTful APIs depending on the use case.
Open research data pilot	<i>Can data be uploaded in an open research data pilot? When?</i> The data will not be uploaded in an open research data pilot.
Embargo periods (if any)	
Archiving & preservation (including storage and backup)	
Managing, storing and curating data	<i>Please describe the modality of storage, backup, transmission, data processing in the short and medium term, with references to practices, standards and regulations where applicable.</i> The data from the ML models will time-stamped and documented. These entries were cross validated with the raw data sources prior to be labelled as valid and ready-to-use in developed algorithms. The database will undergo a backup process (daily/weekly/monthly – will be defined in the next version of DMP) in the respective storages. Data validation will be carried out (e.g., validated through cross checking random samples) so that any inconsistencies identified, will be recorded, and utilized for future references. This information is to ensure that the data maintenance with the highest possible quality and standard. The standard database management principles will be followed to maintain multiple versions of the data, (pre-validated, validated, etc.), to ensure that all data entries are properly peer-reviewed and validated by the experts before merging them with the final validated database.
Data Storage	<i>Please indicate: where data will be stored? the conservation concerns the whole collected data or only part of them? For how long data will be stored?</i> CORE will store the data in distributed DBs (InfluxDB, MongoDB, Apache Druid). The data will be stored for the duration required by AMBIANCE project.

Table 7 - Partner CORE data identification Use Case 2 – SETGA

Data Identification	
Data set description Type of data: qualitative or quantitative? Order of magnitude	<i>Describe the existing or intended data, indicating their origin, nature and order of magnitude.</i> Data set description: Machines' best suitable set of parameters and settings provided by DSS. Type of data: Qualitative Order of magnitude: Unknown. More information will be provided in the following versions of the DMP
Provenance of data: sources	<i>Describe whether the data come from interviews, surveys or are extracted from disciplinary archives, databases and / or other projects, devices, machines...</i> Devices, machines, sensors
Nature and formats of data	<i>Describe nature and format of data:</i> Tables (CSV, ODS, TSV, XLS, SAS, Stata, SPSS portable, hdf5) and/or structured data (JSON).
New data set value	<i>Motivating the creation of the new dataset, defining its added value for the scientific community or other recipients.</i> The developed data will consist on the output of Machine Learning (ML) models and will concern the correlation of the torque and viscosity parameters.
Audio-visual material	<i>In case of video, indicate the duration (the data is useful for planning the costs design and archiving).</i> No audio-visual material will be created.

Partners Activities & Responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device producing the data	CORE
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	CORE
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	SETGA
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	CORE
WPs and tasks	WP3 – T3.3, T3.4
Standards and Metadata	
Metadata standards and data documentation	<i>Describe the type of metadata with reference to standards and documentation.</i> No metadata and data documentation will be created
Methodology for data collection/generation	<i>Describe the methodologies of data collection and production during the research process.</i> 1. Who and how it collects data; CORE will collect the data, produced by the ML models 2. Who and how it structures and stores them; CORE will store the data in distributed DBs (InfluxDB, MongoDB, Apache Druid) in JSON format. 3. Who and how he processes them; The data will be processed by SETGA. 4. Who and how he distributes them. The data distribution will be performed by CORE either through streaming protocols (Kafka, MQTT) or RESTful APIs depending on the use case. More information will be provided in the next version of the DMP.
Data exploitation & sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	Optimization of product quality.
Data ownership	<i>Who is the owner of the data?</i> CORE <i>Is another organization contributing to the data development?</i> No <i>Are you re-using some pre-existing data?</i> No
Suitability for sharing	Confidential
Data utility	<i>How will this data shared/made accessible for verification and re-use?</i> The data will be available either through streaming protocols (MQTT/Kafka) or RESTful APIs depending on the use case.
Open research data pilot	<i>Can data be uploaded in an open research data pilot? When?</i> The data will not be uploaded in an open research data pilot.
Embargo periods (if any)	
Archiving & preservation (including storage and backup)	
Managing, storing and curating data	<i>Please describe the modality of: storage, backup, transmission, data processing in the short and medium term, with references to practices, standards and regulations where applicable.</i> The data from the ML models will time-stamped and documented. These entries were cross validated with the raw data sources prior to be labelled as valid and ready-to-use in developed algorithms. The database will undergo a backup process (daily/weekly/monthly – will be defined in the next version of DMP) in the respective storages. Data validation will be carried out (e.g., validated through cross checking random samples) so that any inconsistencies identified, will be recorded and utilized for future references. This information is performed to ensure that the data maintenance with the highest possible quality and standard. The standard database management principles will be followed to maintain multiple versions of the data, (pre-validated, validated, etc.), to ensure that all data entries are properly peer-reviewed and validated by the experts before merging them with the final validated database.

Data Storage	<p>Please indicate: where data will be stored? the conservation concerns the whole collected data or only part of them? For how long data will be stored?</p> <p>CORE will store the data in distributed DBs (InfluxDB, MongoDB, Apache Druid). The data will be stored for the duration required by AMBIANCE project.</p>
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Table 8 - Partner CORE data identification. Use Case 3 - PODCOMP

Data Identification	
Data set description Type of data: qualitative or quantitative? Order of magnitude	<p>Describe the existing or intended data, indicating their origin, nature and order of magnitude.</p> <p>Data set description: Machines' best suitable set of parameters and settings provided by DSS.</p> <p>Type of data: Qualitative</p> <p>Order of magnitude: Unknown. More information will be provided in the following versions of the DMP.</p>
Provenance of data: sources	<p>Describe whether the data come from interviews, surveys or are extracted from disciplinary archives, databases and / or other projects, devices, machines.</p> <p>Devices, machines, sensors, cameras</p>
Nature and formats of data	<p>Describe nature and format of data:</p> <p>Tables (CSV, ODS, TSV, XLS, SAS, Stata, SPSS portable, hdf5) and/or structured data (JSON).</p>
New data set value	<p>Motivating the creation of the new dataset, defining its added value for the scientific community or other recipients.</p> <p>The developed data will consist of the output of Machine Learning (ML) models and will concern the machines' best suitable set of parameters and settings.</p>
Audio-visual material	<p>In case of video, indicate the duration (the data is useful for planning the costs design and archiving)</p> <p>No audio-visual material will be created</p>
Partners Activities & Responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device producing the data	CORE
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	CORE
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	PODCOMP
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	CORE
WPs and tasks	WP3 – T3.3, T3.4
Standards and Metadata	
Metadata standards and data documentation	<p>Describe the type of metadata with reference to standards and documentation.</p> <p>No metadata and data documentation will be created</p>
Methodology for data collection/generation	<p>Describe the methodologies of data collection and production during the research process.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Who and how it collects data; CORE will collect the data, produced by the ML models Who and how it structures and stores them; CORE will store the data in distributed DBs (MongoDB, Apache Druid) in JSON format. Who and how he processes them; The data will be processed by PODCOMP.

	<p>4. Who and how he distributes them. The data distribution will be performed by CORE either through streaming protocols (Kafka, MQTT) or RESTful APIs depending on the use case. More information will be provided in the next version of the DMP.</p>
<p>Data exploitation & sharing</p>	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	Optimization of product quality
Data ownership	<p><i>Who is the owner of the data?</i> CORE <i>Is another organization contributing to the data development?</i> No <i>Are you re-using some pre-existing data?</i> No</p>
Suitability for sharing	Confidential
Data utility	<i>How will this data shared/made accessible for verification and re-use?</i> The data will be available either through streaming protocols (MQTT/Kafka) or RESTful APIs depending on the use case.
Open research data pilot	<p><i>Can data be uploaded in an open research data pilot? When?</i> The data will not be uploaded in an open research data pilot.</p>
Embargo periods (if any)	
<p>Archiving & preservation (including storage and backup)</p>	
Managing, storing and curating data	<p><i>Please describe the modality of storage, backup, transmission, data processing in the short and medium term, with references to practices, standards and regulations where applicable.</i></p> <p>The data from the ML models will time-stamped and documented. These entries were cross validated with the raw data sources prior to be labelled as valid and ready-to-use in developed algorithms.</p> <p>The database will undergo a backup process (daily/weekly/monthly – will be defined in the next version of DMP) in the respective storages.</p> <p>Data validation will be carried out (e.g., validated through cross checking random samples) so that any inconsistencies identified, will be recorded and utilized for future references. This information is performed to ensure that the data maintenance with the highest possible quality and standard.</p> <p>The standard database management principles will be followed to maintain multiple versions of the data, (pre-validated, validated, etc.), to ensure that all data entries are properly peer-reviewed and validated by the experts before merging them with the final validated database.</p>
Data Storage	<p><i>Please indicate: where data will be stored? the conservation concerns the whole collected data or only part of them? For how long data will be stored?</i></p> <p>CORE will store the data in distributed DBs (InfluxDB, MongoDB, Apache Druid). The data will be stored for the duration required by AMBIANCE project.</p>

2.1.1.4 Partner 4: MONDO

Table 9 - Partner MONDO data identification

Data Identification	
<p>Data set description Type of data: qualitative or quantitative? Order of magnitude</p>	<p><i>Describe the existing or intended data, indicating their origin, nature and order of magnitude.</i></p> <p>Both qualitative and quantitative.</p> <p>- Existing data include materials composition and properties etc., obtained from literature and from previous tests performed by MONDO of other materials for comparison with those to be used and/or developed in the Ambiance project; the existing data can have a size between 1 MB to 10 GB</p> <p>- Intended data include material compositions, processing procedures and properties, etc., of the biomaterials & formulations to be used and/or developed in the Ambiance project; the intended data can have a size between 1 MB to 10 GB</p> <p>Motivate the creation of new data sets and their added value.</p>
<p>Provenance of data: sources</p>	<p><i>Describe whether the data come from interviews, surveys or are extracted from disciplinary archives, databases and / or other projects, devices, machines.</i></p> <p>The data to be generated in the Ambiance project based on the biomaterials & formulations to be used and/or developed will come from materials processing, materials design, manufacturing, testing, simulation and demonstration. Existing data will mostly come from literature, surveys and previous digital twin developments, new tests, and trials from different previous projects where MONDO has been involved.</p>
<p>Nature and formats of data</p>	<p><i>Describe nature and format of data:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) text documents (DOC, ODF, PDF, TXT, etc); b) images (JPG, GIF, SVG, PNG, TIFF); c) video / film (MPEG, AVI, WMV, MP4); d) audio recordings (MP3, WAV, AIFF, OGG, etc); e) simulation models (cas, rocky, dat, inp, odb, db, rst, py, exe, sh, txt) f) tables (CSV, ODS, TSV, XLS, SAS, Stata, SPSS portable); g) extensions from Fluent, Abaqus, Ansys and ROM (.py, .bat, C, CSS, Javascript, Java, etc)
<p>New data set value</p>	<p><i>Motivating the creation of the new dataset, defining its added value for the scientific community or other recipients.</i></p> <p>The biomaterials to be used and the formulations to be developed in the Ambiance project will further unlock the potential of renewable raw materials in applications and in new products, which will further facilitate the reduction of carbon footprint in the targeted sectors and fields. Moreover, the generated data will not only enrich the scientific and technological content in the Ambiance project itself, but also increase know-how of scientific community and industry about sustainable materials, manufacturing and production.</p> <p>The computational models developed in the Ambiance project will contribute to the digitalization of the involved companies towards a more sustainable, efficient, and digital industry. Moreover, the development of these models will also help to advance in the scientific area of simulation.</p>
<p>Audio-visual material</p>	<p><i>In case of video, indicate the duration (the data is useful for planning the costs design and archiving)</i></p> <p>Different videos with an approximated maximum duration of 3-5 min (experimental video records, simulation animations,...)</p>
Partners Activities & Responsibilities	
<p>Partner owner of the device producing the data</p>	<p><i>Partner of the project owner of the device/software producing the data</i></p> <p>Data property of the consortium companies (MONDO, SETGA, PODCOMP)</p>

	The data not intended to be commercially exploited and that might be published either in scientific journals, or by other dissemination channels will be always previously approved by the data owner.
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	AIMEN for SETGA data, RISE for PODCOMP data
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	CORE
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	
WPs and tasks	WP1 (Task 1.1/1.2/1.3), WP2 (Task 2.1/2.2/2.3/2.4/2.5), WP3 (Task 3.1/3.2/3.3/3.4/3.5/3.6), WP4 (Task 4.1/4.2/4.3/4.4), WP5 (Task 5.1/5.2/5.3/5.4/5.5), WP6 (Task 6.1/6.2/6.3), WP7
Standards and Metadata	
Metadata standards and data documentation	<i>Describe the type of metadata with reference to standards and documentation.</i> To be defined
Methodology for data collection/generation	<i>Describe the methodologies of data collection and production during the research process.</i> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Who and how it collects data. MONDO technical operators will gather the data coming from experimental trials and will store them in an internal server (MONDO/ ITAINNOVA) and in a common cloud server (Teams) with restricted access. Computational technical managers will gather data from simulations, models, algorithms, and will store them in an internal server (ITAINNOVA) and in a common cloud server (Teams) with restricted access. Who and how it structures and stores them. Technical managers from ITAINNOVA will structure and store data in the project folder in ITAINNOVA OneDrive and in the defined place in the project folder shared by the Ambiance consortium. Who and how he processes them; appointed responsible from MONDO, AIMEN, CORE with ITAINNOVA support will allocate work to different researchers and engineers who will specifically obtain and process the data. Who and how he distributes them. Internal distributions: R&D responsible from MONDO via technical presentations, reports, etc. <p>External dissemination: Marketing personal from MONDO following the communication & dissemination rules at MONDO, Ambiance consortium and EC.</p>
Data exploitation & sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	MONDO will use the data for fabrication process optimization, improving product quality, new materials research, and reduce the costs associated to production and material consumption.
Data ownership	<i>Who is the owner of the data?</i> MONDO <i>Is another organization contributing to the data development?</i> Companies members of the Ambiance consortium (SETGA and PODCOMP. Also, eventually ITAINNOVA, AIMEN and CORE <i>Are you re-using some pre-existing data?</i> Yes
Suitability for sharing	<i>Public/confidential/limited access:</i> confidential for external use but can be shared to some AMBIANCE consortium partners if required.
Data utility	<i>How will this data shared/made accessible for verification and re-use:</i> Mainly through scientific publication on peer reviewed journals, presentations in conferences and demonstrations in workshops, always

	observing confidentiality agreements and previously consulting involved parties
Open research data pilot	<i>Can data be uploaded in an open research data pilot? When?</i> The data can be uploaded in an open research data pilot if and when they will be published in e.g., journal papers, conference abstracts/presentations, always observing confidentiality agreements and previously consulting involved parties
Embargo periods (if any)	No
Archiving & preservation (including storage and backup)	
Managing, storing and curating data	<i>Please describe the modality of storage, backup, transmission, data processing in the short and medium term, with references to practices, standards and regulations where applicable.</i> All data generated by MONDO will be collected, stored, and backed up in an internal server of ITAINNOVA, and those who will be shared will be placed in folders in Teams and OneDrive.
Data Storage	<i>Please indicate: where data will be stored? the conservation concerns the whole collected data or only part of them? For how long data will be stored?</i> At least the time that the EU Commission recommends for each project.

Partner 5: SETGA

Table 10 - Partner SETGA data identification

Data Identification	
Data set description Type of data: qualitative or quantitative? Order of magnitude	<i>Describe the existing or intended data, indicating their origin, nature, and order of magnitude.</i> 3D model and CAD design of the demonstrator. (usually around 500kb to 10 MB)
Provenance of data: sources	<i>Describe whether the data come from interviews, surveys or are extracted from disciplinary archives, databases and / or other projects, devices, machines.</i> The data to be generated in the AMBIANCE project based on the design of the demonstrator.
Nature and formats of data	<i>Describe nature and format of data:</i> CAD files (.DWG, .SLDDRW, .SLDWPRT, .STEP) Text documents (PDF)
New data set value	<i>Motivating the creation of the new dataset, defining its added value for the scientific community or other recipients.</i> This data will be used for the fabrication of the demonstrator with an optimal design for large format 3D printing.
Audio-visual material	<i>In case of video, indicate the duration (the data is useful for planning the costs design and archiving)</i> To be determined
Partners Activities & Responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device producing the data	SETGA
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	AIMEN
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	
WPs and tasks	WP4 (T4.1, T4.3)
Standards and Metadata	
Metadata standards and data documentation	<i>Describe the type of metadata with reference to standards and documentation.</i> To be defined
Methodology for data collection/generation	<i>Describe the methodologies of data collection and production during the research process.</i> 1. SETGA elaborates a design according to its experience and the AMBIANCE project requirements for the demonstrator. 2. AIMEN modifies the design and makes recommendations according to the requirements of large format 3D printing. 3. SETGA adapts the design to the recommendations (iterative process). 4. AIMEN validates the final design.
Data exploitation & sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	AIMEN will use the data for the manufacturing of the demonstrator.
Data ownership	<i>Who is the owner of the data?</i> SETGA <i>Is another organization contributing to the data development?</i> AIMEN <i>Are you re-using some pre-existing data?</i> No
Suitability for sharing	Confidential/Sensitive for external use, open for AMBIANCE consortium partners
Data utility	<i>How will this data shared/made accessible for verification and re-use?</i>
Open research data pilot	<i>Can data be uploaded in an open research data pilot? When?</i>

	Public data will be disseminated, when relevant, and agreed with partners. Data would be available in open dissemination research data repositories such as Zenodo
Embargo periods (if any)	
Archiving & preservation (including storage and backup)	
Managing, storing and curating data	<p><i>Please describe the modality of storage, backup, transmission, data processing in the short and medium term, with references to practices, standards and regulations where applicable.</i></p> <p>Storage; locally on AIMEN and SETGA servers and on the project repository. Backup; AIMEN and SETGA server Transmission; email and project repository. Data processing in the short and medium term, with references to practices, standards, and regulations where applicable.</p>
Data Storage	<p><i>Please indicate: where data will be stored? the conservation concerns the whole collected data or only part of them? For how long data will be stored?</i></p> <p>Data will be stored locally on the servers of AIMEN and SETGA for the duration of the project and the justification period. Part of the data set might be stored on an open data repository – TBD during the project. At least the time that the EU Commission recommends for each project.</p>

2.1.1.5 Partner 6: PODCOMP

Table 11 - Partner PODCOMP data identification

Data Identification	
<p>Data set description Type of data: qualitative or quantitative? Order of magnitude</p>	<p><i>Describe the existing or intended data, indicating their origin, nature and order of magnitude.</i></p> <p>- Existing data include quantitative technical properties on materials and structures in the form of excel sheets from earlier measurements or technical data sheets and material safety data sheets received from suppliers of materials or from literature for comparison, all to be used as initial requirements and references. It can also comprise blueprints for moulds to be optimized for the new processes. Existing data can be in the range 1 MB-50 GB</p> <p>- Intended data comprises all results from measured properties of the new materials and products as well as tds and sds for all new materials that will be used (such data most likely already exist but will be new for POD). CAD, solidworks or DWG files and CNC programming exclusively made for the new products and processes that will be developed in Ambiance will be included.</p> <p>Films and images taken at different stages of development. Intended data can be in the range 10 MB-50 GB</p> <p>Motivate the creation of new data sets and their added value.</p> <p>The data that is generated during the project will be important for the development of new biocomposites. Cad/CNC files may be used for creation of digital twins and optimization of processing and will probably be shared within the project.</p>
<p>Provenance of data: sources</p>	<p><i>Describe whether the data come from interviews, surveys or are extracted from disciplinary archives, databases and / or other projects, devices, machines..</i></p> <p>The data to be generated in the Ambiance project based on the biomaterials & biocomposites to be used and/or developed will come from composite design, process optimization, testing, simulation and demonstration. Existing data will mostly come from literature and possibly material suppliers.</p>
<p>Nature and formats of data</p>	<p><i>Describe nature and format of data:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) text documents (DOC, ODF, PDF, TXT, etc); b) images (JPG, GIF, SVG, PNG, TIFF); c) video / film (MPEG, AVI, WMV, MP4); f) tables (CSV, ODS, TSV, XLS, SAS, Stata, SPSS portable); g) source codes (C, CSS, JavaScript, Java, etc); j) cad cam, dwg, solid works
<p>New data set value</p>	<p><i>Motivating the creation of the new dataset, defining its added value for the scientific community or other recipients</i></p> <p>The biomaterials to be used and the biocomposites to be developed in the Ambiance project will further unlock the potential of renewable raw materials in broadened applications and in new products for civil purpose. The focus on using hardy grass and agricultural waste and with the goal to only use the inherent binders of the plants to make composites with an energy efficient development and processing, should make the products we develop quite efficient carbon sinks contributing to a low carbon society. The knowledge and associated data will increase the awareness of potential of low environmental impact materials and products.</p>
<p>Audio-visual material</p>	<p><i>In case of video, indicate the duration (the data is useful for planning the costs design and archiving)</i></p> <p>Around 1-3 min</p>
Partners Activities & Responsibilities	
<p>Partner owner of the device producing the data</p>	Podcomp (POD)
<p>Partner in charge of the data collection</p>	

(if different)	
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	
WPs and tasks	WP1 (Task 1.1/1.2/1.3), WP2 (Task 2.1), WP3 (Task 3.2/3.5), WP4 (Task 4.1/4.4/4.5), WP5 (Task 5.1/5.3), WP6 (Task 6.1/6.2/6.3)
Standards and Metadata	
Metadata standards and data documentation	<i>Describe the type of metadata with reference to standards and documentation</i>
Methodology for data collection/generation	<p><i>Describe the methodologies of data collection and production during the research process.</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Who and how it collects data; As reference and requirements on the materials and products to be developed, existing data will be collected from literature search on the web and possibly from material suppliers. Data will be generated by testing of materials, developing new moulds and optimizing the processing as well as by documenting the development in writing, photos or films. 2. Who and how it structures and stores them; The project manager at Podcomp, Birgitha Nyström prepares a folder for the project on the Podcomp server. Each type of development task will have a dedicated subfolder to make it easy for the staff involved to save relevant data in the correct folder which makes it easy for others to find them. 3. Who and how he processes them; The project manager Birgitha Nyström and the development engineer Daniel Eklund will oversee all the development work and give access to store and use files in the Ambiance folder to those involved in the project development work. 4. Who and how he distributes them. The project manager Birgitha Nyström is responsible for distribution of work and access to the project data. If external parties want to use data generated at Podcomp, the project leader or the steering group at Podcomp will take decision whether it is suitable to share them. <p>Refer to regulations or practices in force in the scientific community of reference</p>
Data exploitation & sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	We will use digital tools to select and optimize the products and processes in AMBIANCE. By simulating the compression molding and placement of sensors etc will allow us to identify necessary adjustments before building the actual tools. This will reduce the costs of tools and make the overall development efficient.
Data ownership	<p><i>Who is the owner of the data?</i> Podcomp</p> <p><i>Is another organization contributing to the data development?</i> Other partners are likely to contribute to the data development through the collaboration work for testing of materials, integration of sensors.</p> <p><i>Are you re-using some pre-existing data?</i> Material data from previous projects may be used as reference but the products to be developed will be new for us.</p>
Suitability for sharing	<i>Public/confidential/limited access:</i> confidential for external use but some data will be shared with AMBIANCE consortium if required
Data utility	<i>How will this data shared/made accessible for verification and re-use?</i> Data related to product development will most likely not be shared but generic data can be presented at workshops and conferences.
Open research data pilot	<p><i>Can data be uploaded in an open research data pilot? When?</i></p> <p>Data can be uploaded in an open research data pilot if they are not crucial for protecting our product development, this can be done as soon as we have decided that they are not crucial.</p>
Embargo periods (if any)	

Archiving & preservation (including storage and backup)	
Managing, storing and curating data	<p><i>Please describe the modality of storage, backup, transmission, data processing in the short and medium term, with references to practices, standards and regulations where applicable.</i></p> <p>All data generated by Podcomp will be collected, stored and backed up according to Podcomp's ordinary data storing taking the rules and policy regarding GDPR into account.</p>
Data Storage	<p><i>Please indicate: where data will be stored? the conservation concerns the whole collected data or only part of them? For how long data will be stored?</i></p> <p>All data generated by Podcomp will be collected, stored, and backed up according to Podcomp's ordinary data storing.</p>

2.1.1.6 Partner 7: RECENDT

Table 12 - Partner RECENDT data identification

Data Identification	
Data set description Type of data: qualitative or quantitative? Order of magnitude	<i>Describe the existing or intended data, indicating their origin, nature and order of magnitude.</i> THz absorbance data of biomaterial used to show the long-term stability of the panels. Data set will be created using the equipment and material developed in AMBIANCE.
Provenance of data: sources	<i>Describe whether the data come from interviews, surveys or are extracted from disciplinary archives, databases and / or other projects, devices, machines...</i> Data will be measured from materials developed by ambiance consortium.
Nature and formats of data	<i>Describe nature and format of data:</i> Series of either 1D or 2D data (absorbance locally distributed) as a function material and moisture values, stored as text data.
New data set value	<i>Motivating the creation of the new dataset, defining its added value for the scientific community or other recipients.</i> New data set is necessary to be able to create data-based models using THz absorbance to determine material moisture.
Audio-visual material	N/A
Partners Activities & Responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device producing the data	RECENDT
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	
WPs and tasks	WP3, Task 3.2.2
Standards and Metadata	
Metadata standards and data documentation	<i>Describe the type of metadata with reference to standards and documentation.</i> Metadata will be added as comments to the CSV files.
Methodology for data collection/generation	<i>Describe the methodologies of data collection and production during the research process.</i> 1. Who and how it collects data; 2. Who and how it structures and stores them; 3. Who and how he processes them; 4. Who and how he distributes them. <i>Refer to regulations or practices in force in the scientific community of reference.</i> Data will be collected by THz absorbance locally distributed (1D or 2D) and the database will be structured similar to Zenodo.
Data exploitation & sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	The data will be used to develop a method for product moisture measurement in the field.
Data ownership	<i>Who is the owner of the data?</i> <i>Is another organization contributing to the data development?</i> <i>Are you re-using some pre-existing data?</i> This is a new dataset, which will be owned by RECENDT. PODCOMP and RISE will contribute providing the material for measurement,
Suitability for sharing	Confidential

Data utility	<i>How will this data shared/made accessible for verification and re-use?</i> Data will not be shared.
Open research data pilot	<i>Can data be uploaded in an open research data pilot? When?</i> No
Embargo periods (if any)	5 Years
Archiving & preservation (including storage and backup)	
Managing, storing, and curating data	<i>Please describe the modality of storage, backup, transmission, data processing in the short and medium term, with references to practices, standards and regulations where applicable.</i> Data will be stored at RECENDT and AMBIANCE file server, which is regularly backed up...
Data Storage	<i>Please indicate: where data will be stored? the conservation concerns the whole collected data or only part of them? For how long data will be stored?</i> For at least the project run time the full data will be stored. After the project end only, the relevant data will be stored for at least 7 years. The other data will be deleted if file space is running out.

2.1.1.7 Partner 8: RISE

Table 13 - Partner RISE data identification

Data Identification	
Data set description Type of data: qualitative or quantitative? Order of magnitude	<i>Describe the existing or intended data, indicating their origin, nature and order of magnitude.</i> - Existing data include materials composition and properties etc., obtained from literatures and from previous tests performed by RISE of other materials for comparison with those to be used and/or developed in the Ambiance project; the existing data can have a size between 1 MB to 10 GB - Intended data include material compositions, processing procedures and properties, etc., of the biomaterials & biocomposites to be used and/or developed in the Ambiance project; the intended data can have a size between 1 MB to 10 GB Motivate the creation of new data sets and their added value.
Provenance of data: sources	<i>Describe whether the data come from interviews, surveys or are extracted from disciplinary archives, databases and / or other projects, devices, machines..</i> The data to be generated in the Ambiance project based on the biomaterials & biocomposites to be used and/or developed will come from materials processing, composite design, manufacturing, testing, simulation and demonstration. Existing data will mostly come from literatures and previous tests from different projects that RISE is involved and from RISE database.
Nature and formats of data	<i>Describe nature and format of data:</i> a) text documents (DOC, ODF, PDF, TXT, etc); b) images (JPG, GIF, SVG, PNG, TIFF); c) video / film (MPEG, AVI, WMV, MP4); d) audio recordings (MP3, WAV, AIFF, OGG, etc); f) tables (CSV, ODS, TSV, XLS, SAS, Stata, SPSS portable); i) database (MS Access, MySql, Oracle, ect) The ones that are not likely to be used at the moment are deleted.
New data set value	<i>Motivating the creation of the new dataset, defining its added value for the scientific community or other recipients.</i> The biomaterials to be used and the biocomposites to be developed in the Ambiance project will further unlock the potential of renewable raw materials in broadened applications and in new products for civil purpose, which will further facilitate the reduction of carbon footprint in the targeted sectors and fields. Moreover, the generated data will not only enrich the scientific and technological content in the Ambiance project itself, but also increase know-how of scientific community and industry about sustainable materials, manufacturing, and production.
Audio-visual material	<i>In case of video, indicate the duration (the data is useful for planning the costs design and archiving)</i> Around 3-5 min
Partners Activities & Responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device producing the data	Research Institutes of Sweden (RISE)
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	
WPs and tasks	WP1 (Task 1,1/1.2), WP2 (Task 2.1/2.2/2.3/2.5), WP3 (Task 3.1/3.2/3.5), WP4 (Task 4.1/4.4), WP5 (Task 5.1/5.2/5.3/5.4/5.5), WP6 (Task 6.2/6.3)

Standards and Metadata	
Metadata standards and data documentation	<i>Describe the type of metadata with reference to standards and documentation</i> To be defined.
Methodology for data collection/generation	<i>Describe the methodologies of data collection and production during the research process.</i> 1. Who and how it collects data; The project manager at RISE, Guan Gong, will collect data to be generated in different processing, testing and simulation of biomaterials and biocomposites to be used and/or developed in the Ambiance project. 2. Who and how it structures and stores them; The project manager at RISE, Guan Gong, will structure and store data in the project folder in RISE OneDrive, and in the defined place in the project folder shared by the Ambiance consortium. 3. Who and how he processes them; The project manager at RISE, Guan Gong, will allocate work to different researchers and engineers at RISE who will specifically obtain and process the data, and Guan will monitor the data processing. 4. Who and how he distributes them. The project manager at RISE, Guan Gong, will be in charge of distributing data according to the suggestions from her colleagues who perform specific work, and following the communication & dissemination rules at RISE, Ambiance consortium and EC. <i>Refer to regulations or practices in force in the scientific community of reference.</i>
Data exploitation & sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	RISE will use the data for optimization of raw materials refining and composite manufacturing, improving composite product quality, new materials research and to reduce the costs associated to materials refining and biocomposite product production.
Data ownership	<i>Who is the owner of the data?</i> RISE <i>Is another organization contributing to the data development?</i> All other partners will very likely contribute to the data development, such as through the collaboration work for modification of the manufacturing process and integration of sensors as well as demonstration and prototyping. <i>Are you re-using some pre-existing data?</i> Yes, we will try to reuse some previous data for e.g., virtual testing, and for comparison with Ambiance results.
Suitability for sharing	<i>Public/confidential/limited access:</i> confidential for external use but can be shared to AMBIANCE consortium if required
Data utility	<i>How will this data shared/made accessible for verification and re-use:</i> Mainly through scientific publication on peer reviewed journals, presentations in conferences and demonstrations in workshops
Open research data pilot	<i>Can data be uploaded in an open research data pilot? When?</i> The data can be uploaded in an open research data pilot if and when they will be published in e.g., journal papers, conference abstracts/presentations.
Embargo periods (if any)	No
Archiving & preservation (including storage and backup)	
Managing, storing and curating data	<i>Please describe the modality of storage, backup, transmission, data processing in the short and medium term, with references to practices, standards and regulations where applicable.</i> All data generated by RISE will be collected, stored and backed up in RISE OneDrive until new rules, e.g., new archiving domain and new storing time, will be applied.

Data Storage	<p><i>Please indicate: where data will be stored? the conservation concerns the whole collected data or only part of them? For how long data will be stored?</i></p> <p>All data generated by RISE will be collected, stored and backed up in RISE OneDrive until new rules, e.g., new archiving domain and new storing time, will be applied.</p>
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2.1.1.8 Partner 9: SUPSI

Table 14 - Partner SUPSI data identification

Data Identification	
Data set description Type of data: qualitative or quantitative? Order of magnitude	<i>Describe the existing or intended data, indicating their origin, nature and order of magnitude.</i> (Quantitative) LCI data on production process input flows, collected from the shopfloor and used for LCA assessment of the pilot cases.
Provenance of data: sources	<i>Describe whether the data come from interviews, surveys or are extracted from disciplinary archives, databases and / or other projects, devices, machines..</i> Data are related to machines performances and retrieved from the field (observation) or from existing databases/simulated data.
Nature and formats of data	<i>Describe nature and format of data:</i> Structured data collected in Excel file (.xlsx)
New data set value	<i>Motivating the creation of the new dataset, defining its added value for the scientific community or other recipients.</i> The data collected will be part of the digital twin of the production lines considered and are necessary to calculate the environmental impacts of the new products developed in the project.
Audio-visual material	<i>In case of video, indicate the duration (the data is useful for planning the costs design and archiving).</i> N/A
Partners Activities & Responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device producing the data	SUPSI
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	SUPSI, with the support of each pilot responsible
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	
WPs and tasks	WP1 (T1.3), WP3 (T3.6), WP4(T4.1, T4.2, T4.3, T4.4, T4.5)
Standards and Metadata	
Metadata standards and data documentation	<i>Describe the type of metadata with reference to standards and documentation</i>
Methodology for data collection/generation	Describe the methodologies of data collection and production during the research process. The data collection will be performed as following: 1. SUPSI create the awareness on LCA methodology and used LCA tool among the consortium through a dedicated webinar; 2. SUPSI supports partners in modelling their production processes and collected the necessary data to characterize the input flows by using an Excel file; 3. SUPSI models processes by using an LCA tool; 4. Impact indicators are estimated by using a LCA tool and ecoinvent database, and shared with the partners
Data exploitation & sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	The calculated data will be used to validate benefits of the new products.
Data ownership	<i>Who is the owner of the data?</i> <i>Is another organization contributing to the data development?</i> <i>Are you re-using some pre-existing data?</i> SUPSI and contributing partners
Suitability for sharing	<i>Public/confidential/limited access.</i>

	To be agreed: raw data are expected to be confidential, impact data could be displaced as open according to confidentiality request by pilot responsible.
Data utility	<i>How will this data shared/made accessible for verification and re-use?</i> Elaborated data will be made accessible in an excel file (.csv)
Open research data pilot	<i>Can data be uploaded in an open research data pilot? When?</i> To be agreed (depending on "suitability for sharing")
Embargo periods (if any)	
Archiving & preservation (including storage and backup)	
Managing, storing and curating data	<i>Please describe the modality of storage, backup, transmission, data processing in the short and medium term, with references to practices, standards and regulations where applicable.</i> Data will be stored in AMBIANCE cloud storage and processed in short term.
Data Storage	<i>Please indicate: where data will be stored? the conservation concerns the whole collected data or only part of them? For how long data will be stored?</i> Data will be stored in AMBIANCE cloud storage.

2.1.1.9 Partner 10: CRIT

Table 15 - Partner CRIT data identification

Data Identification	
Data set description Type of data: qualitative or quantitative? Order of magnitude	<i>Describe the existing or intended data, indicating their origin, nature, and order of magnitude.</i> Data are also collected in DEC tasks. At the first stage of the project (M1-M18), the collected data derive from website and social media analytics and from the attendance in fairs or conferences.
Provenance of data: sources	<i>Describe whether the data come from interviews, surveys or are extracted from disciplinary archives, databases and / or other projects, devices, machines.</i> The data collected in the DEC task derive from website and social media analytics and from the attendance in fairs or conferences.
Nature and formats of data	<i>Describe nature and format of data:</i> - text documents (DOC, PDF, TXT, etc), such as reports, deliverables, papers, from DEC tasks. - images (JPG, GIF, SVG, PNG, TIFF) from DEC tasks. - video / film (MPEG, AVI, WMV, MP4) from DEC tasks.
New data set value	<i>Motivating the creation of the new dataset, defining its added value for the scientific community or other recipients.</i> The data collected in the DEC tasks are used to identify potential stakeholders to involve in the future exploitation actions and trainings.
Audio-visual material	<i>In case of video, indicate the duration (the data is useful for planning the costs design and archiving).</i> Video will be between 1 and 5 min long.
Partners Activities & Responsibilities	
Partner owner of the device producing the data	CRIT is the owner of data produced in the context of Dissemination and Exploitation activities since it is the leader of the WP5. CORE is the owner of data produced in Communication task. All project partners are owners of the data they provide for communication, dissemination and exploitation activities (such as: event participation, publication, news, press release...).
Partner in charge of the data collection (if different)	-
Partner in charge of the data analysis (if different)	-
Partner in charge of the data storage (if different)	-
WPs and tasks	WP5 T.5.1, T5.2, T5.3
Standards and Metadata	
Metadata standards and data documentation	<i>Describe the type of metadata with reference to standards and documentation.</i> Metadata will be: - descriptive , giving information on the data discovery and identification (titles, author, keywords). E.g., public deliverables. - administrative , outlining when and how data was created, file type and other technical information, and who can access it (Dataset name, version, description, format, License, keywords). E.g., excel file created by CRIT to monitor KPIs for Dissemination activities.
Methodology for data collection/generation	<i>Describe the methodologies of data collection and production during the research process.</i> Communication: CORE is responsible to collect info for the communication activities and publish on the project website and social media. CRIT is responsible for the KPIs monitoring of the activity.

	Dissemination/Exploitation: CRIT is responsible to collect partners contribution via a Microsoft form/excel file stored in the company SharePoint. CRIT is responsible for the KPIs monitoring of the activity.
Data exploitation & sharing	
Data exploitation (purpose/use of the data analysis)	To identify potential stakeholder to involve in the future exploitation actions and trainings.
Data ownership	<i>Who is the owner of the data? CRIT/CORE and all project partners Is another organization contributing to the data development? All project partners. Are you re-using some pre-existing data? No.</i>
Suitability for sharing	<i>Public/confidential/limited access. Public or limited access depending on the data (such as confidential deliverable vs public deliverables).</i>
Data utility	<i>How will this data shared/made accessible for verification and re-use?</i> In DEC activity most of the data will be made public via the project website and social media. Partners will reserve the right to select confidential material (such as results, deliverable that outlined strategic activities for the project partners).
Open research data pilot	<i>Can data be uploaded in an open research data pilot? When?</i> Yes, as soon as the publication is ready after a peer review and approved by the partner who wrote it and/or participated in it.
Embargo periods (if any)	-
Archiving & preservation (including storage and backup)	
Managing, storing, and curating data	<i>Please describe the modality of storage, backup, transmission, data processing in the short and medium term, with references to practices, standards, and regulations where applicable.</i> Communication: data will be stored, backup, transmitted by CORE using the company repository and process by both CRIT and CORE for the KPIs monitoring phase. Dissemination/Exploitation: data will be stored, backup, transmit and process by CRIT using the company SharePoint.
Data Storage	<i>Please indicate: where data will be stored? the conservation concerns the whole collected data or only part of them? For how long data will be stored?</i> Data for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation will be stored both on partners' private repository and in the project repository.

2.1.2 Comments and considerations

Data set template was sent to all partners to collect or update information already provided at M6 on the type of data they expect to produce during their activities. All partners have provided updated table at M18 of project activities. Some questions in the table have not been answered because at the time of this writing partners are still defining some methodology in data management and sharing.

3 Horizon Europe Questionnaire Template

To ensure the correctness and fully description and management the data management life cycle, the Horizon Europe DMP template⁵ has been take as guideline for the writing of AMBIANCE DMP. The current version of the DMP is updated at M18 of the project. The document, that will be further updated and augmented with new datasets and results during the lifespan of AMBIANCE (namely at M36 and M48). For completing the DMP deliverable, partners have provided inputs following the HEU questionnaire template as well as the Data Set Template, which will be the basis to fill in and expand in the following months as consortium partners will be requested to investigate and provide more detailed information on their produced data and whether these are discoverable, accessible, assessable, and intelligible, useable (beyond the original purpose) and interoperable.

3.1 DMP training and workshops

Data Management requires an overall approval from the partners. To take right decisions about DMP, training actions will be carried out to inform partners about how to manage project dataset and formal requests from HEU.

A first online workshop was organised by CRIT (Data manager) at M2 to train the consortium about the data management guidelines in Horizon Europe and brainstorm together about the data that would be generated and collected in AMBIANCE project. The workshop was held via Klaxoon, at this link: <https://app.klaxoon.com/join/QVWJNUG>.

After the DPM training, partners were asked to brainstorm on the concepts of data utility and exploitation. In the second phase of the brainstorming session, the partners were asked to answer three questions for each category of data in order to assess data characterization:

1. What type of data will be generated?
 - Origin, size, format
 - Are they confidential or publishable?
 - Are there any sensitive information (privacy and ethics)
2. Who can use these data? Who is interested in them (third parties)?
3. How can we use these data?
 - Internally: partners, tasks/WPs
 - Externally: communication/dissemination

The data brainstorming has been carried out for each WP, to better consider all the activities expected in AMBIANCE. The collected information has been used to fill the initial version of the data summary in the DMP at M6. Since the DMP is a living document, the workshop was mainly focussed on the first stage of the project (M1-M18). Further workshops will be organised to update the internal policy about DMP and the related deliverable.

⁵ <https://enspire.science/wp-content/uploads/2021/09/Horizon-Europe-Data-Management-Plan-Template.pdf>

3.2 Data Summary

What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Figure 1 - AMBIANCE concept for bio-based product manufacturing

The main AMBIANCE objective is to introduce sustainable products in urban outdoor applications by developing bio-based materials and optimizing manufacturing processes. To succeed in the goal, a wide variety of data will be collected or generated, and they will be the main decision support tools to identify the best paths towards AMBIANCE ambitions.

The AMBIANCE concept (Figure 1 - AMBIANCE concept for bio-based product manufacturing) requires a strong interpenetration between the various activities to reach the goals and a continuous exchange of information and data. Each AMBIANCE WP will be both provider and users of data, in particular:

- **WP1 (Industrial requirements and specifications)** objective is to draw a clear picture of each use case, from the production line descriptions to the objectives. The information collected in this WP were fundamental to set up the right strategy in selecting and developing bio-based materials (WP2) and optimizing manufacturing processes (WP3). Furthermore, information has been the starting point for WP4 tasks: to effectively manage the demonstration activities and as baseline for LCA and impact and techno-economic assessment. At the time of this writing this WP is concluded.
- **WP2 (Development of novel Bio-based materials)** is focused on the selection and development of bio-based material and data concerning material characterization and testing. These data are used by the consortium to define and develop the best material composition for the three use cases, which will also implemented in demonstration activities. The data are also used in WP3 with the aim to include the material properties and processing characteristics in manufacturing monitoring systems.
- **WP3 (Optimization of bio-based product manufacturing processes)** includes the tasks to optimize the manufacturing process. It will provide monitoring tools, based on collected data in manufacturing processes and the WP1 and WP2 data, to improve bio-based product processes. The collected data will allow to properly define the manufacturing operating windows for biomaterials and develop digital twins able to support the offline setting up of the new manufacturing processes.
- **WP4 (Validation, demonstration and assessment)** will incorporate the data from the previous WPs (WP1-WP3). Indeed, these data will be used to properly set up the demonstrators of each use case and reach the objective expected in AMBIANCE. The data from the research and development WPs will

be also used to carry out the LCA and impact and techno-economic assessment and demonstrate sustainability performances of AMBIANCE demos.

- WP5 (Impact Enhancement) is the connection between the project and the external audience. The data generated in the other WPs are used in DEC activities, based on the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary". The WP also collects data from target groups to better address the DEC activities in function of the audience and organize the training sessions.
- WP6 (Project Coordination) is dedicated to the activities for the proper project management. Data from the other WPs are used regularly to check the status of the activities and to establish strategies to mitigate and reduce risks.

What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect?

A non-exhaustive list of types and formats of data was provided to partners (see from Table 2 - Partner ITAINNOVA data identification to Table 15 - Partner CRIT data identification) to define the most common data types and format that will be generated within the project. According to the consortium the main formats are:

- text documents (DOC, ODF, PDF, TXT, etc), such as reports, deliverables, papers, etc.;
- images (JPG, GIF, SVG, PNG, TIFF) from research, use cases and DEC tasks;
- video / film (MPEG, AVI, WMV, MP4) from research, use cases and DEC tasks;
- audio recordings (MP3, WAV, AIFF, OGG, etc) from research, use cases and DEC tasks;
- simulation models (cas, rocky, dat, inp, odb, db, rst, py, exe, sh, txt) for simulation and modelling tasks;
- tables (CSV, ODS, TSV, XLS, SAS, Stata, SPSS portable) containing textual/numerical data (strings) and quantitative and qualitative information, including;
 - Bio-materials properties and characterization;
 - Monitoring parameters;
 - Processing parameters;
 - Personal Data connected to DEC and training tasks.
- source codes (C, CSS, JavaScript, Java, etc) for modelling;

Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Most of the data collected in AMBIANCE are directly generated during project's activities. Some partners will reuse existing data, mainly in bio-based materials and digital twin development.

The consortium uses existing data as baseline for the selection and optimization of bio-based materials in WP2 (Development of novel Bio-based materials). In this context, ITAINNOVA use data from literature, tests, and trials from its previous projects to select and benchmark the most promising bio-based thermoplastics, compatibilizers and additives for MONDO and SETGA use cases. RISE and PODCOMP also use existing data from literature, material suppliers and previous research project to set the baseline for composition and processing parameters for self-bonded straw composite.

Existing data are also used to set up the WP3 (Optimisation of bio-based product manufacturing processes) tasks. The partners' previous experience and data is employed in the early stage of the WP to design and develop proper advanced monitoring systems. ITAINNOVA use the data from previous digital twin development projects.

What is the origin of the data?

The data mainly arise from research and development WPs. At the first stage of AMBIANCE project (M1-M18), data are mostly generated by WP1, WP2 and WP3.

In WP1 data are collected from the three use cases to identify the main requirements and objectives of each value chain and define the baseline for the pilot assessment. The data are mainly provided by the use cases by visiting the plants and sharing reports about the processes. If needed, interviews from research partners will be used to collect further data.

In WP2, the generated data concern the properties and characterization of bio-based materials. For each use case, different materials and compositions are tested and characterized by several characterization techniques. All the generated information is used to optimize the bio based-materials that will be implemented in the demos.

WP3 is focussed on material manufacturing processes. Real time data are collected from use cases (MONDO, SETGA, PODCOMP) manufacturing equipment to determine key process parameters and operation windows. Furthermore, the data are used to create digital twins and advanced monitoring systems to enable the fabrication optimization, and its integration into the manufacturing process.

Data are also collected in DEC tasks. At the first stage of the project (M1-M18), the collected data will derive from website and social media analytics and from the attendance in fairs or conferences. This data concerns mainly.

What is the expected size of the data?

In AMBIANCE project, it is not expected to generate an extended amount of data. The project does not include Big Data technologies neither wide trial that involve a large number of experiments or analysis. At the first stage of the project the size can be estimated in 5-10 Terabyte. Based on the first results, the size of data will be updated in the further version of DMP.

To whom might it be useful ('data utility')?

At the first project stage, the generated and collected data are mainly used internally. The needed data are shared among the partners to enable the research and development activities expected in the WPs.

The DEC activities is in charge to increase the use of the generated data outside the consortium. In this first project phase, scientific papers would be written and published, based on the obtained results. The papers will consider the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" with the aim to share the non-confidential data with the scientific community. The data produced in AMBIANCE project can be used by worldwide researchers as baseline for current and future projects about bio-based materials and manufacturing process optimization. The DEC team is in charge to provide information about the project by means of website, social media and newsletters. These tools allow to preliminary involve stakeholders and understand how they might potentially utilize the generated data within AMBIANCE.

3.3 FAIR data

The principles of FAIR data have been established by a set of different stakeholders like academia, industry, funding agencies, and scholarly publishers. According to Wilkinson et al. (2016), the FAIR Data Principles are a set of guiding principles in order to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (Figure 2).

Figure 2 - FAIR Data Principle

The FAIR Data Principles clearly provide a concise and measurable set of parameters that should be respected to ensure the availability and reusability of data for further research purposes by third parties that are not part of the project. Distinct from peer initiatives that focus on the human scholar, the FAIR Principles put specific emphasis on enhancing the ability of machines to automatically find and use the data, in addition to supporting its reuse by individuals. The mentioned principles do not necessarily propose an explicit technology, standard or implementation solution, forego implementation choices and promote the maximum usage of data.

More detailed information on how to make data findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable will result from discussions among partners and in future updated version of the DMP (M36, M48).

3.3.1 Making data Findable, including provisions for metadata

The AMBIANCE project is focused on securing that the produced data will be identifiable and easily discoverable by the interested stakeholders and beneficiaries. Most of the data produced within the project are discoverable with metadata and identifiable and locatable by means of a standard persistent identifier (mainly DOI). Furthermore, to make the internal identification easier, partners decided upon a common naming procedure to be used in the project Teams namely ITAINNOVA MS Teams (AMBIANCE [name of the document]), considering internal project conventions. However, partners also rely on their internal company system for data identification.

Furthermore, all the collected/generated datasets are accompanied by metadata for facilitating their findability. Metadata provides additional information that helps data consumers better understand the meaning of data, its structure, and to clarify other issues, such as rights and license terms, the organization that generated the data, data quality, data access methods and the update schedule of datasets. Metadata have a twofold nature: descriptive, therefore giving information on the data discovery and identification (titles, author, keywords) and administrative outlining when and how data was created, file type and other technical information, and who can access it (Dataset name, version, description, format, License, keywords).

In AMBIANCE, metadata standards are not applicable due to the multidisciplinary nature of the project. The consortium aims, when possible, to use **DOI as persistent identifiers**, so for each dataset **at least the DOI Kernel Metadata Declaration**⁶ will be ensured. In addition to DOI Kernel Metadata, metadata will include the following information: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue, and embargo); Horizon Europe funding; grant project name, acronym, and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organizations and the grant, as requested

⁶ https://www.doi.org/doi_handbook/4_Data_Model.html

by AMBIANCE GA. Further metadata might be added, following a versatile format based on the publishing body (Zenodo, Open Research Europe, etc.). The inclusion of search keywords in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use will be further discussed in the upcoming months. Since AMBIANCE policy is to subscribe the DOI Kernel Metadata Declaration, the metadata will be easily harvested and indexed by means already in use for DOI system.

3.3.2 Making data openly Accessible

According to Art. 17 of the AMBIANCE Grant Agreement, digital research data generated in the action ('data'), must:

- as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP, deposit the data in a trusted repository; if required in the call conditions, this repository must be federated in the EOSC in compliance with EOSC requirements.
- as soon as possible and within the deadlines set out in the DMP, ensure open access — via the repository — to the deposited data, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or a licence with equivalent rights, following the principle 'as open as possible as closed as necessary', unless providing open access would in particular:
 - be against the beneficiary's legitimate interests, including regarding commercial exploitation, or
 - be contrary to any other constraints, in particular the EU competitive interests or the beneficiary's obligations under this Agreement; if open access is not provided (to some or all data), this must be justified in the DMP.
- provide information via the repository about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to re-use or validate the data.

In this contest, the AMBIANCE consortium give access to the generated/collected data, based on the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary". Most of data generated within the project are confidential: for instance, some data such as production order number, are sensitive, because they give information about current capacity/efficiency/etc and should be encrypted and transformed into an accessible version. However, some data will be made public if anonymized at the end of the project. Most of the non-confidential data will be uploaded on online certified repositories like Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>) or other platforms and made accessible to stakeholders and the public outside of the project using standard software and methods. The use of certified and trusted repositories and DOI system ensure that the sharable data are easily accessible outside the consortium.

In this version of the DMP each partner has specify which on data (at M18) will be made openly available as the default and the time of availability. An embargo might be applied in case partners would publish or seek protection of the intellectual property: the duration will be defined once the intellectual property to be protected will be fully delineated.

At the current stage of the project the data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited in the servers of each partner's organisations or in internal project repository's such as the ITAINNOVA MS Teams and will be made publicly available at the end of the project. People involved in the project have access to the internal project repository and they can read/modify/download data connected to their tasks. The versioning chronology provided by MS Teams keeps track of the identity of the person accessing the data. Since no sensitive data are involved in AMBIANCE tasks, there is no need for a data access committee.

In AMBIANCE project, **for each dataset at least the DOI Kernel Metadata Declaration⁷ is ensured** and the metadata are also included the information required by the GA. The metadata will be generally open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles. If there are any exceptions in openly publishing metadata, motivations will be reported in the next DMP version.

⁷ https://www.doi.org/doi_handbook/4_Data_Model.html

3.3.3 Making data Interoperable

According to the consortium, most of the data produced in the project are interoperable, and data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. is favoured. However, partners still have to define which metadata vocabularies, standards and methodologies will be used at this end. Generally, interoperable data use a formal, standard, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation, vocabularies that follow FAIR principles and standard data-storage methods. On the contrary non-interoperable data use vocabularies, standards and methodologies that primarily answer to internal efficiency and safety requirements.

3.3.4 Increase data Re-use (through clarifying licences)

As already shown in Partners' data identification tables, some data generated within the project are to be reused by third parties including academia and industry stakeholders. If some project data will be licensed to permit their re-use by the external stakeholders, **Creative Commons or GNU licenses will be used**. The data that are made available for individuals that are external to the project are included in the project deliverables marked as public. Such data are made public, through the project's website and open access repositories for scientific publications such as Zenodo and other Institutional Repositories connected with OpenAIRE, as soon as they will be approved by the project officer on the Funding and Tenders Platform of the EC.

3.4 Other research outputs

Within AMBIANCE, other research outputs will be produced (e.g. testing methodology, manufacturing decision support systems, etc.). During the project, these outputs will be evaluated to understand their exploitation potential. If they will be considered not exploitable by the partners, an open sharing strategy would be considered for these kinds of outputs.

3.5 Allocation of resources

The estimation of the costs to be incurred when making the data FAIR according to the principles of the EC and the proper allocation of the resources to do are two topics addressed by the DMP. Moreover, the plan identifies the responsibilities for data management in project describing the costs and potential value of long-term preservation. Even if this is an early stage of the project (M18) as not all the points could find an exhaustive description, this chapter of the DMP will address the costs for making data FAIR in AMBIANCE, how these costs will be covered, who will be the responsible for the data management and who will decide and how what data will be kept and for how long.

3.5.1 Estimation of cost

The costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the HEU grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions). Costs are eligible for reimbursement during the duration of the project under the conditions defined in the HEU Grant Agreement.

3.5.2 Responsibilities for data management

The partner who is responsible for data management is CRIT as detailed in GA. CRIT is in charge to periodically update the DMP with further details and information provided by all project partners that should provide their contributions.

3.6 Data security

According to AMBIANCE Grant Agreement, § 5.2 Data protection, AMBIANCE will use state-of-the-art technologies for secure storage, delivery, and access of personal information, as well as managing the rights of the users. In this way, there will be complete guarantee that the accessed, delivered, stored, and transmitted content will be managed by the right persons, with well-defined rights, at the right time. Data security procedures will be enacted AMBIANCE for technical data deriving from use cases and research centre and personal data from DEC activities.

All data are captured and stored anonymously in partner companies' internal repositories and in the project's Internal collaboration platform (see WP6 - Project coordination). A wide range of precautions and countermeasures is adopted to preserve privacy and ensure data protection and safeguard human rights and

ethical principles (e.g., formal written informed consent will be obtained; data will be as much as possible anonymous).

3.7 Ethical aspects

Ethical aspects are not involved in AMBIANCE tasks. Personal data (name, surname, job, mail address, phone number, etc.) collected during DEC activities will be processed according to the Articles 12, 13 and 14 of the European Regulation 2016/679 of the 27th of April 2016 on the protection of natural persons, with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (“GDPR” in the following, namely General Data Protection Regulation).

4 Conclusions

The first updated version of the DM is presented and delivered in this document describing how acquired data and knowledge will be shared and/or made open as well as how data will be maintained and preserved during and after the timeline of the AMBIANCE project.

Partners have provided answers within the HEU questionnaire survey according to the provisions of the national legislation that are in line with the respective EU Directives for Data Management and ethics and within the Data Set template to investigate the type of data they expect to collect during the project’s lifespan. Starting from this last template, project data will be identified throughout the lifespan of the project, and they will be provided in a way to define relevant knowledge, increase partners’ awareness, validate results and timeframe of various actions. Additionally, all partners will be responsible to periodically update information on their research and subject data.

Lastly, connections with WP5 Impact Enhancement have been established to link the outcomes of conducted research work and ongoing relevant technological developments, generating useful data, to the dissemination and exploitation strategy of AMBIANCE.

The 3rd version of the DMP will be provided by M36.